

Development of a flow biocatalytic-based platform for electrochemical monitoring of urea in wastewater

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ABSTRACT

The early evaluation of urea content in water and wastewater is of utmost importance for preventing pollution and improving remediation technologies, also related to urea conversion into a valuable energy product. In this work, a customized urease-based potentiometric platform for the detection of urea in wastewater samples was developed. Amino-functionalized glass beads were used as support material for urease immobilization in a customized bioreactor; then, using an online flow measurement setup, the NH_4^+ produced by the enzymatic reaction was measured by means of a potentiometric sensor housed in a customized flow cell. Operational and analytical parameters were optimized to achieve the best bioreactor performance. An in-depth study of the composition of the measurement buffer was also carried out; its influence on the sensitivity and detection limits was investigated, demonstrating that a careful selection of its concentration needs to be performed based on the type of samples to be analyzed ($\text{LOD} = 8.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ M}$). Finally, at the optimized operative conditions, the full system was applied to the determination of urea in spiked wastewater samples. Using the standard addition method, an average percentage of recovery of $102 \pm 5 \%$ was obtained for the analyzed samples despite the interferences present, demonstrating a possible application of the developed setup for remote online urea monitoring in wastewaters.

1. Introduction

The ever-increasing demand for cultivated products and the subsequent intensification of farming practices have made the use of urea-based fertilizers more widespread than ever [1]. As a result, significant amounts of urea inevitably seep into water systems via agricultural runoff, ultimately contaminating receiving water bodies [2]. This contamination has harmful consequences for aquatic ecosystems, as urea contributes, together with other ammonium-based fertilizers, to eutrophication, a process that promotes excessive algal blooms, leading to oxygen depletion and significant ecological damage [3,4]. Furthermore, urea is present in high concentrations in mammals' urine. Thus, beyond agricultural runoff, urea also enters water systems through municipal wastewater and animal waste streams, making it a prominent contaminant in both industrial and domestic effluents. Rapid detection methods are crucial for effective real-time monitoring and

quantification of urea levels in aquatic environments [5], for preventing pollution and improving remediation technologies, also related to H_2 production [6–8]. Indeed, the electrooxidation of urea, present at high concentration in wastewater, converts urea into a valuable energy product (i.e. H_2). Recently, the utilization of urea-rich wastewater for producing useful fuel has been gathering increasing attention due to society's need for alternative energy sources. Thus, for this reason, there is the need to characterize the wastewater on its content in urea [9–11].

At present, several analytical techniques are employed for the quantification of urea [12], including HPLC-based methods [13]. While these methods provide accurate results, they are often resource-intensive, requiring costly equipment and highly trained personnel. Furthermore, they are typically unsuitable for *in situ* and online monitoring, as they involve complex sample preparation procedures and laboratory-based analyses. These limitations highlight the necessity for developing alternative methodologies that enable

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real-time, on-site quantification of urea and other contaminants in water systems [14,15].

By contrast, colorimetric kits and urease-based potentiometric biosensors can be used in decentralized analysis and have been used in clinical settings for many years. Different types of colorimetric kits are commercially available: some of them employ urease and glutamate dehydrogenase [16], and some others are based on the formation of a colored complex of urea with a chromogenic reagent [17]. These kits, however, are prone to issues related to interference, such as ammonium naturally present in wastewater samples, as well as samples characterized by high turbidity levels or inherent coloration. Potentiometry is less prone to being affected by turbidity and the presence of interferences in the samples, but it has been scarcely applied to wastewater analysis [12]. Indeed, only a few examples of potentiometric biosensors have been tested for urea environmental analysis so far (Table S1).

Herein, a customized urease-based bioreactor was designed and applied to urea potentiometric determination in an online flow configuration for real time monitoring of urea in wastewater. The immobilized enzyme is contained in a small reactor in a flow system. Controlled pore amino-functionalized glass beads were used as support materials for urease immobilization. The effluent from the bioreactor, containing the ammonium ions produced by the enzyme-promoted hydrolysis of urea, is passed into a flow-through cell housing an NH_4^+ potentiometric sensor. The bioreactor is operated under such conditions that the substrate is converted to the product with the maximum efficiency. A fine tuning of the different parameters involved in bioreactor assembly was performed by using a chemometric approach, based on Design of Experiment (DoE) and Response Surface Methodology (RSM), in order to maximize the signal output and minimize the amount of the reagents used [18,19]. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that a RSM approach is used for the optimization of a urease-based bioreactor coupled to a potentiometric sensor for online flow monitoring of urea levels in wastewaters.

After a preliminary investigation of the analytical performances of the potentiometric sensor, the best experimental conditions for urea determination were optimized. Particular attention was devoted to the selection of the measuring buffer, which must be carefully selected based on the type of samples to be analyzed. Finally, the developed bioreactor was tested for urea determination in wastewater samples. The obtained results demonstrate that such an approach could be useful for addressing the growing environmental challenges posed by urea contamination, offering a means for a real time assessment of the quality of the aquatic ecosystems and wastewaters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Urea, NaOH, $(\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})$, $(\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O})$, NaCl, Na_2SO_4 , KH_2PO_4 , KCl, NH_4Cl , Peptone from soybean (enzymatic digest) suitable for microbiology, Glutaraldehyde Grade I (25 % in H_2O) were purchased by Merck (Milan, Italy). Urease TCI from Jack Bean (EC 3.5.1.5, 300 units/mg) was purchased from VWR (Milan, Italy). Controlled Pore Glass AminoPropyl beads (lot. 168982, reported pore diameter of 500 Å, particles size 120–200 mesh, amine content 139 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) were purchased from LGC Biosearch Technologies (Hoddesdon, United Kingdom).

Peristaltic pump model MINIPULS3 was purchased from Gilson (Milan, Italy). Potentiometer model HI-5222 double channel was purchased from Hanna Instruments (Milan, Italy). Ion-selective combined ammonium electrode (NH_4^+ -ISE) model 3051 was purchased from DirectION (Dover, UK). Plastic cylinders (length 40 mm, inner diameter 5 mm, outer diameter 13 mm), mesh-equipped caps, connections for bioreactor assembly, and the polymethyl methacrylate-based flow cell used for in-flow NH_4^+ measurements were designed and produced in-house.

2.2. Samples

Four wastewater samples were collected from the same location at the inlet of an Italian treatment plant processing urban and municipal wastes. After collection, each sample was stored in 0.5 L polyethylene bottles and immediately refrigerated at $+4^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis, to minimize chemical and biological alterations.

Urea-free synthetic human urine was used to simulate analysis in urine samples. Once prepared, synthetic urine was fractioned, filtered to remove the suspended protein fraction, diluted 1:50 in 500 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.0 and spiked with different urea concentrations.

2.3. Software

MODDE Pro Version 13.0.2 software (Sartorius Data Analytics, Göttingen, Germany) was employed for planning 3-level Full Factorial Design (FFD) used in the optimization step and for the related data treatment in RSM. The experiments described in FFD experimental plan were run in a randomized order.

2.4. Measurement scheme

2.4.1. Measurements set-up

A block scheme of the measurement set-up is reported in Fig. 1a. A peristaltic pump is used to introduce the sample in the bioreactor, where urea is hydrolyzed by urease to produce NH_4^+ and CO_2 . The NH_4^+ produced is potentiometrically measured by the NH_4^+ -ISE. Fig. 1b shows a scheme of the bioreactor. The measurement is performed in a customized flow cell (Fig. 1c); the potential value is recorded vs. time (Fig. 1d). The ΔmV is the analytical data which is proportional to the urea content.

2.4.2. Bioreactor assembly

The protocol for the preparation of the bioreactors involves two main steps: a) activation of glass beads; b) beads functionalization with the enzyme. Both are performed using an in-flow setup. Regarding step a): plastic cylinders are filled with 120 mg of aminopropyl glass beads and a volume of solution containing glutaraldehyde prepared in a 100 mM phosphate buffer pH = 7.0. The two ends of each cylinder are then closed with mesh-equipped caps, connected to the fittings and placed in-flow at a flow rate of 0.2 mL min^{-1} for 1h 30 min. After this period of time, each cylinder is then washed with 50 mL 100 mM phosphate buffer pH = 7.0 (flow rate 0.2 mL min^{-1}) before passing to the next step. To carry on step b): a solution containing a fixed concentration of urease prepared in a 100 mM phosphate buffer pH = 7.0 is introduced in the cylinder containing the activated beads and placed in flow in a closed loop overnight at the flow rate of 0.2 mL min^{-1} .

Finally, the obtained bioreactor is washed by flushing it with 500 mM phosphate buffer pH = 7.0 at a flow rate of 0.2 mL min^{-1} for 30 min. The bioreactor can then be stored for subsequent use.

2.5. Response Surface Methodology for parameters optimization

An RSM study was carried out to optimize the parameters for the preparation of the bioreactor, making it possible to draw a detailed map of the predicted response throughout the experimental domain and thus to obtain the combination of settings that gave the best performance [20]. To perform the experiment, a 1.0 M urea solution (prepared in 500 mM phosphate buffer pH 7.0) was left to run in the bioreactor at a flow rate of 0.2 mL min^{-1} . Then, the outlet solution was collected and diluted 1:30 in the same buffer for the potentiometric measurement. The output potential value obtained for each reactor was considered as a response to carry out this study.

The considered factors were glutaraldehyde concentration and urease amount, which were studied in the following experimental domain: glutaraldehyde, 0.5–2.5 % v/v; urease, 3.0–9.0 mg mL^{-1} . The hypothesized relationship between the factors (x_i) and the response (y)

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up: a) Schematic representation of the instrumental set-up for urea online flow measurements; b) bioreactor; c) flow cell; d) example of potential vs. time signal.

consisted of a polynomial quadratic model, represented by Equation (1):

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_{11} x_1^2 + \beta_{22} x_2^2 + \beta_{12} x_1 x_2 + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where y is the response (potential), β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_2 are the linear terms, β_{11} and β_{22} are the quadratic terms, β_{12} is the interaction term, ε is the experimental error and the factors are designated by x_1 (glutaraldehyde) and x_2 (urease).

In order to estimate the model coefficients, a 3-level FFD was used [21]. In this kind of design, the matrix includes every combination of factors' levels, and the number of experiments is $3^k + n$, where k is the number of factors to be studied, and n is the number of replicates at the center of the experimental domain for the estimate of the experimental variance.

3. Results and discussion

The coupling of the urease-based bioreactor with the potentiometric NH_4^+ -ISE sensor for the determination of urea in wastewaters is described in Fig. 1. The wastewater is sampled and introduced in the bioreactor, where urea is hydrolyzed by urease with the formation of NH_4^+ and CO_2 . The NH_4^+ produced is potentiometrically measured. Preliminary experiments were devoted to evaluate the best experimental conditions to perform the measurements.

3.1. NH_4^+ -ISE sensor performances

The NH_4^+ potentiometric response obtained for the ISE sensor is reported in Fig. 2. The sensor shows a quasi-Nernstian behavior, with a slope of 51.3 ± 0.2 mV/decade in deionized water, and a linear response within a concentration range from $1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to 1.0 M ($R^2 = 0.996$). A similar experiment was carried out for Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+} , respectively. These ions are common components of wastewater matrices and could act as interferents for the potentiometric measurements of NH_4^+ . As shown in Fig. 2, the response of the sensor to Na^+ and Ca^{2+} does not increase up to $1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M and 0.5 M, respectively. A different behavior is observed for K^+ ; in this case, the sensor shows a not negligible response in the concentration range from $1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to 1.0 M. This is also confirmed by the values of the selectivity coefficients (calculated using the separate solution method [22]) that are $(8.79 \pm 0.08) \cdot 10^{-2}$, $(5.28 \pm 0.05) \cdot 10^{-4}$, and $<1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$, for K^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} , respectively. Therefore, while K^+ can constitute an important interferent in the determination of the NH_4^+ , Na^+ and especially Ca^{2+} have a more limited effect and only at very high concentrations.

The NH_4^+ -ISE sensor was then applied to the determination of NH_4^+ levels in four samples of municipal wastewater entering a water treatment and purification plant. For each sample, the NH_4^+ content was quantified, without applying any pretreatment, by using the Standard Addition Method [23]; the obtained results were compared with those obtained with a standard spectrophotometric reference method [24]. As

Fig. 2. Potentiometric response of the NH_4^+ -ISE sensor for NH_4^+ in deionized water in the concentration range $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ - 1.0 M. A comparison with potentiometric responses for major interfering ions as Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+} in the same concentration range is also reported. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation ($n = 3$).

it can be seen from Table 1, the NH_4^+ concentration values obtained with the two different methods are in good agreement. The Pearson correlation coefficient [25] was calculated to be 0.998, p -value = 0.13, $n = 3$.

3.2. Influence of the buffer composition

The ionic strength is a crucial parameter in potentiometric measurements, as it influences the activity of the ions to be measured. For this reason, it is convenient to keep it controlled and constant during the analysis. Furthermore, for urea determination, the pH value plays an important role, since the NH_4^+ ions and the carbon dioxide produced influence the pH of the measuring solution, which must be kept in the range of 7.0–8.0 in order to retain the maximum urease activity [26]. Thus, the selection of a suitable measurement buffer is mandatory.

Table 1

NH_4^+ content in four samples of municipal wastewater analyzed using the standard spectrophotometric method and the NH_4^+ -ISE sensor.

Sample n.	Standard spectrophotometric method (mM)	NH_4^+ -ISE sensor (mM)
1	2.0 ± 0.2	2.11 ± 0.03
2	2.7 ± 0.3	2.90 ± 0.04
3	4.5 ± 0.5	4.48 ± 0.03
4	4.1 ± 0.5	4.08 ± 0.05

Among the various possibilities, phosphate buffer is recognized as one of the best medium, as reported in literature [27]. Particular attention must be devoted to the choice of the counterion; being K^+ a strong interferent and avoiding Ca^{2+} ions (due to the low solubility of its phosphate salts), Na^+ was selected as counterion.

Fig. 3a shows the influence that NH_4^+ concentrations have on the final pH value of different phosphate buffer compositions at pH 7.0. As can be observed, the higher the buffer concentration is, the lower is the effect of the added NH_4^+ on the final pH value. For all the tested buffers, the pH remains stable in the NH_4^+ concentration range $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6} - 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M (unlike for deionized water). For NH_4^+ concentrations higher than $1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M, the buffering capacity becomes more influencing. Indeed, in the case of the 500 mM phosphate buffer, NH_4^+ does not affect the pH for the full concentration range tested, whereas for 50 and 10 mM phosphate buffer a pH variation can be observed starting from an NH_4^+ concentration of $1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M. This is an important finding, because it demonstrates how critical is the buffering capacity. In the case of samples with high urea content (for example samples from septic tanks or from animal effluents), a more concentrated buffer is necessary; conversely, for samples of wastewater in which urea contents will be lower (i.e. outlets), a lower buffering capacity could be suitable.

Buffer concentrations could also influence the detection limit of the measurements due to the Na^+ content, as demonstrated by the NH_4^+ calibration curves obtained in 10, 50 and 500 mM phosphate buffer (Fig. 3b). As can be observed, the slope of the linear portion remains unchanged, while the NH_4^+ detection limit shifts towards higher values, as the buffer (and therefore the Na^+) concentration increases. In Table 2, the limits of detection (LOD) [28] and limits of quantification (LOQ) [29] for NH_4^+ are reported.

It can be observed that the LOD value in a 10 mM phosphate buffer is very close to that found in deionized water, whereas it increases by almost two orders of magnitude passing from 10 mM to 500 mM. This has to be carefully considered for the analysis of real samples. In wastewater samples for which the expected urea-derived NH_4^+ (urea- NH_4^+) content is low, such as drinking water [30], 10 mM phosphate buffer pH 7.0 turns out to be suitable for the quantification of NH_4^+ . However, for samples with higher urea- NH_4^+ content, such as industrial [31], municipal [32] and animal farm wastewaters [33], a higher buffer concentration must be used.

3.3. Reagent optimization by DoE in bioreactor assembly

Once the analytical performances of the NH_4^+ -ISE sensor were characterized, the bioreactors were assembled, by immobilizing the enzyme urease on controlled pores aminopropyl glass beads as solid support.

Table 2

Linearity range, LOD, and LOQ evaluated for the NH_4^+ -ISE in different mediums: deionized water and phosphate buffer pH 7.0 at different concentrations.

Solution	Linearity range (M)	LOD (M)	LOQ (M)
Deionized water	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5} - 1.0$	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
10 mM Phosphate buffer	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-5} - 1.0$	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
50 mM Phosphate buffer	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4} - 1.0$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
500 mM Phosphate buffer	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3} - 1.0$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Several requirements must be achieved for immobilizing an enzyme on a solid support: a) the enzymatic activity should not be altered to any significant degree; b) the immobilized enzyme must be stable, so that the enzymatic activity will be preserved through several reaction cycles; c) the overall cost of the immobilization procedure must be affordable (i.e. significantly reduced or at least not increased). Controlled pore aminopropyl glass beads have been described extensively in the literature as a solid support for enzymes in bioreactors [34]. The amine groups of the glass beads are susceptible to cross-linking with glutaraldehyde, a common crosslinking agent, that links the enzyme to glass beads. Nevertheless, an important issue is the control of the degree of cross-linking by controlling the amount of glutaraldehyde. In fact, the activity of the immobilized enzyme can be reduced excessively if too much cross-linking agent is used. On the other hand, if the amount of cross-linking agent is too low, a leakage of the enzyme is possible, and the lifetime of the bioreactor is reduced. Furthermore, the amount of cross-linking agent is related to the amount of the enzyme used. By a proper selection of the amount of glutaraldehyde toward the amount of enzyme, it is possible to obtain a balance of high enzyme activity and long endurance, while achieving a high percentage of conversion of enzyme-substrate to the measurable product. In order to optimize the reagents involved in the bioreactor assembly, the effect of the glutaraldehyde and enzyme amount was studied as a 2-factors system by using RSM chemometric approach. The experimental domain of the factors was selected on the basis of data reported in literature [34–36] and the results of preliminary experiments (data not shown). In particular, the experimental domain for glutaraldehyde was selected considering that values lower than 0.5 % v/v could compromise enzyme endurance and values higher than 2.5 % v/v might impair enzyme reaction efficiency. Conversely, the lower level for the enzyme was selected to ensure an efficient conversion of the enzyme-substrate to the end product, while values higher than 9.0 were excluded for minimizing the cost of analysis. Due to the limited number of factors considered and the preliminary information already available, it was possible to directly define the experimental domain to be investigated by RSM.

Fig. 3. Effect of NH_4^+ concentration on the pH of the buffer: a) pH variation vs. added NH_4^+ in phosphate buffer at different concentrations (10, 50, 500 mM at pH 7.0); b) Calibration curves of NH_4^+ in different medium: deionized water, 10, 50 and 500 mM phosphate buffer pH 7.0.

To obtain the experimental data necessary for the study, several bioreactors were prepared by combining different urea and glutaraldehyde concentrations, according to the FFD shown in Table 3, for a total number of 12 combinations (9 experiments + 3 replicates at the center). In addition to them, two more bioreactors were prepared, one containing untreated glass beads while the second one was empty (blanks). Each bioreactor was then tested using a 1.0 M urea solution prepared in pH 7.0 sodium phosphate buffer at a concentration of 500 mM to have the greatest buffering capacity. In this way, by keeping constant urea concentration and flow rate, the variation in potential value can be only related to the combination of the bioreactor components. In Table 3 the ΔmV measured vs. glutaraldehyde and urease concentrations are reported. Experiments performed with blanks gave negligible signals (lower than the background noise) and data are not shown.

The response was statistically treated and the model was refined by deleting a non-significant quadratic term, resulting in the final calculated model:

$$y = 94.6 + 2.5x_1 + 9.1x_2 - 5.2x_2^2 - 3.0x_1x_2$$

where y is the potential, x_1 is glutaraldehyde concentration (as v/v%) and x_2 is urease enzyme concentration (as mg mL⁻¹).

This model was found valid and significant by ANOVA and very good values of coefficient of determination R^2 and goodness of prediction Q^2 were found: $R^2 = 0.992$, $Q^2 = 0.959$, reproducibility = 0.994 [23]. The graphical analysis of coefficients is shown in Fig. S1a and provides a visual representation of the model terms to determine their significance. Each bar corresponds to a term of the model and its length is proportional to the weight of the coefficient. A significant term is one that has an uncertainty level that does not extend across $y = 0$. A relevant positive linear effect and a negative quadratic effect of urease were noticed. The linear effect of glutaraldehyde was significant but of lower weight, and a negative interaction was found between glutaraldehyde and urease. Contour plot is reported in Fig. S1b, by plotting urease vs. glutaraldehyde. The maximization of ΔmV value is obtained in the red zone, at high levels of glutaraldehyde and urease. Anyway, it can be highlighted that values of ΔmV higher than 95.0 mV can be obtained also at medium levels of urease and at high levels of glutaraldehyde. Thus, with the aim of minimizing analysis cost while achieving high response, the value of urease was set at 6 mg mL⁻¹, while glutaraldehyde was fixed at the highest level, corresponding to 2.5 % v/v. Hence, applying these optimized conditions the measured ΔmV was 97.6 ± 0.7 mV ($\alpha = 0.025$, $n = 3$), a value which fell inside the predicted interval (95.9–98.2 mV).

3.4. Flow rate optimization

Once optimized the reagent concentrations, the flow rate for online measurement was also evaluated. For this purpose, a $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M urea solution, prepared in 500 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.0, was

Table 3

Full Factorial Design (FFD) with the different combinations of urease and glutaraldehyde used to assemble the bioreactors. 12 combinations (9 experiments + 3 replicates) were finally tested.

Exp. No.	Glutaraldehyde (% v/v)	Urease concentration (mg mL ⁻¹)	ΔmV
1	0.5	3.0	75.8
2	1.5	3.0	79.4
3	2.5	3.0	85.8
4	0.5	6.0	90.9
5	1.5	6.0	95.4
6	2.5	6.0	97.6
7	0.5	9.0	99.5
8	1.5	9.0	98.4
9	2.5	9.0	97.7
10	1.5	6.0	94.9
11	1.5	6.0	94.8
12	1.5	6.0	94.0

loaded into the system and left to flow until reaching a steady-state response condition; different flow rates were tested, from 0.1 to 3.0 mL min⁻¹. The results are reported in Fig. 4a–b. In particular, Fig. 4a shows the potential values obtained for the tested flow rates as a function of the measurement time. It can be observed that the lower the flow rate, the longer the measurement takes to reach a steady-state condition. However, for flow rates in the range 0.1–1.0 mL min⁻¹ the potential values at the steady-state are very similar. By contrast, they decrease for higher flow rates, probably because the contact time between the enzyme and the analyte is too short, as shown by the ΔmV vs. flow rate values reported in Fig. 4b. Based on these experimental data, the flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹ was chosen to carry on further experiments.

3.5. Calibration curves of urea in phosphate buffer

Once all critical parameters were optimized, calibration curves of urea in a concentration range from $1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to 1.0 M were performed in sodium phosphate buffer. Fig. 5a shows the calibration curves obtained for different buffer concentrations, 10, 50 and 500 mM respectively. It can be observed that, as for the calibration curves for NH₄⁺, there is a shift of the linearity range to higher urea concentrations, with the subsequent increase in the LOD values, from $8.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $3.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M passing from 10 to 500 mM sodium phosphate buffer, respectively (Table 4).

Therefore, as already mentioned, the buffer selection constitutes a critical point of the measurement and must be carefully selected considering the nature of the samples and the amount of urea to be determined.

The slope of the calibration curves in 500 mM phosphate buffers, pH 7.0 obtained for urea is 51.4 ± 0.4 mV/decade; considering the quasi-Nernstian behavior of the NH₄⁺-ISE sensor, with a slope of 51.3 ± 0.2 mV/decade in deionized water, it is possible to conclude that the urea is converted to ammonia within the bioreactor with 100 % efficiency over the corresponding linear range (Table 4). Indeed, the maximum efficiency of the bioreactor is strictly dependent on pH variation, so that this parameter must be checked for each type of sample.

The stability of the bioreactors was also evaluated, by testing four bioreactors over time using a $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M urea solution; three of them (named from #1 to #3) were stored at +4 °C, whereas one bioreactor (named as #4) was stored at room temperature in dark condition. The results are shown in Fig. 5b; it can be seen that the potential response is similar for all the tested bioreactors (response average: 23 ± 1 mV), independently from the storage conditions. In particular, Fig. 5b shows stability over time higher than 120 days without significant signal decay, confirming the robustness of the assembly methodology and the reproducibility of the functionalization process.

3.6. Application to real sample analysis

As already stated, the urea content in real samples can be very different, being strictly dependent on sample type (environmental vs. biological samples). The highest content is expected in urine samples. Some reported urea concentrations in urine from pigs are in the range 198–335 mM [37,38], and from around 153 to 763 mM [39]; in human urine, the average urea concentration is around 300 mM [40].

Considering that a possible application of the proposed analytical platform is the monitoring of the biofluid-septic tanks and the wastewater effluent from the farming settings, some preliminary experiments were performed to evaluate the analytical behavior of the bioreactor in this type of matrix. Indeed, urine contains various organic substances but also many inorganic salts, which could constitute an interference in the potentiometric measurements. Thus, a urea calibration curve in a diluted urea-free synthetic human urine [26] was performed (Fig. 5c). In these experimental conditions, a linear response for urea in the concentration range $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ - $1.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$ M was obtained (42.4 ± 0.5 mV/log[Urea], $R^2 = 0.998$), with a LOD of $6.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M. This is the same

Fig. 4. Flow rate optimization experiments: a) Potential values recorded vs. measurement time during the flowing of a 1.0 mM urea solution in 500 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.0; b) ΔmV reported vs. flow rate. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation ($n = 3$).

Fig. 5. a) Urea calibration curves reported as ΔmV vs. urea concentration, performed in 500, 50 and 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.0, respectively, b) Stability over time of four bioreactors; #1, #2 and #3 stored at 4 °C and #4 stored at room temperature. Tests were performed on 1 mM urea solution, c) Urea calibration curve obtained spiked synthetic urine solution obtained by plotting the signal vs. the added urea concentration.

linearity range obtained for the calibration curve in the 500 mM phosphate buffer; however, in this case a higher slope is observed (51.4 ± 0.5 mV/log[Urea]); this difference is probably due to a matrix effect related to the synthetic urine composition, as previously discussed. In any case, the approach is sensitive enough to be applied to the determination of urea in this kind of matrices.

Then, the measurements in the four inlet wastewater samples were carried out. To perform the experiments, the samples were filtered through a 0.45 μm filter to remove suspended matter, then spiked with urea in order to achieve a final concentration of 300 mM and finally diluted 1:10 in 500 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7.0. The analysis was carried out by using the Standard Addition Method. Table 5 shows the recovery results obtained for each sample.

As can be observed, a very high recovery percentage was obtained for all four samples, with a deviation from the added concentration of no more than 5 %. It is also interesting to note that the urea over- or underestimation does not depend on the NH_4^+ content of the sample, demonstrating that there is no effect of its presence on the urea quantification using the bioreactor-based system coupled with a potentiometric NH_4^+ sensor. This is an interesting advantage of the proposed

Table 4
Analytical performances of the proposed method in 10, 50 and 500 mM sodium phosphate buffers, pH 7.0.

Phosphate buffer concentration (mM) pH = 7.0	Linearity range (M)	LOD (M)	LOQ (M)
10	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-5} - 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
50	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-4} - 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
500	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} - 1.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 5
Recovery values for Urea (300 mM) spiked in municipal wastewater samples.

Sample n.	Observed Urea (mM)	Recovery %
1	295 ± 2	98 %
2	315 ± 3	105 %
3	299 ± 3	99 %
4	311 ± 4	104 %

method over some colorimetric kits.

To better explain this concept, it should be noted that preliminary experiments aimed to characterize the wastewater for the urea content with commercially available colorimetric kits demonstrated that kits based on the reaction chaired by NADH, α -ketoglutarate and glutamate dehydrogenase are prone to the interference of NH_4^+ present in the wastewater, even in diluted samples. Sample turbidity could have also a detrimental effect on the colorimetric measurements. So, a careful selection of the analytical conditions has to be performed by using the colorimetric kits. The measurements performed with the proposed

potentiometric platform are less prone to interference from turbidity and NH_4^+ contents. As a further remark, it should be noted that the NH_4^+ content (or any eventually interferents on the response of the potentiometric sensor) in the sample can be promptly evaluated by temporarily excluding the reactor during this operation by introducing a T-valve in the flow system. This approach is useful for monitoring and controlling NH_4^+ levels in real-time, while ensuring the continuity of the process. Subsequently, the measurement of urea can be carried out by restoring the flow within the reactor.

4. Conclusions

A potentiometric biocatalytic-based setup has been successfully developed for the analysis of urea in different types of wastewaters. Operational parameters for performing the measurements were optimized; particular attention was given to the selection of the measurement buffer, which was chosen to minimize potentiometric interferences with the sensor while maintaining adequate buffering capacity for the enzymatic activity. By varying the concentration and ionic strength of the buffer, it is possible to modulate the linearity ranges and LODs, adapting them to the type of sample being analyzed. This versatility allows the system to be applied to samples with both high urea content (such as those from intensive livestock farms) and lower urea content (such as effluent from wastewater treatment plants). Moreover, in addition to being suitable for online measurements, the approach developed in this work has the advantage of not being affected by the presence of interferents such as NH_4^+ , which is naturally present in wastewater samples, unlike most commercially available urea colorimetric kits. Finally, stability trials demonstrated that the optimized bioreactors can be used for more than 4 months without losing activity. This is an excellent premise for a possible application of the potentiometric biocatalytic-based platform for remote online monitoring of urea.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lorenzo Quadrini: Investigation, Writing – original draft, Validation, Visualization. **Serena Orlandini:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Serena Laschi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Claudio Ciccone:** Supervision, Project administration. **Filippo Catelani:** Conceptualization, Provision of study materials. **Iliaria Palchetti:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.127755>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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